

**Learning from green chemistry
for Safe-by-Design**

This report presents the results of a brief study into the rise and impact of green chemistry as a movement within the field of chemistry, and offers suggestions for strengthening the role of Safe-by-Design as an emerging policy approach.

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Author

Dr Daan Schuurbiens

De Proeffabriek

Josef Israelslaan 63
6813 JB Arnhem
t: +31 6 143 652 16
e: daan@proeffabriek.nl
w: www.proeffabriek.nl

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Summary

The concept of green chemistry— designing chemical products and processes in such a way that the production and emission of hazardous substances is reduced or even completely avoided – originated in response to an increasing discontent with the production of hazardous waste by the chemical industry in the 1980s and 1990s. The United States Environmental Protection Agency (EPA) introduced the concept along with the Pollution Prevention Act of 1990. Over the last 25 years, green chemistry has developed into a relatively influential movement within the field of chemistry, primarily in the United States and the United Kingdom and, to some extent, also in Europe.

This report, commissioned by the Dutch National Institute for Public Health and the Environment (RIVM) presents the findings of a short-term study into the rise of green chemistry. The study approached green chemistry as a *movement*: it studied not only the substantive meaning of the term (e.g. the definition of the concept, the nature of the principles, and the various applications and savings realised) but in particular also the history of its origin, in other words: how did the concept come into being? Who were the champions of the movement? How did they try to generate attention for the concept? Accordingly, the study does not make any statements about the degree to which green chemistry has actually contributed to making chemistry ‘greener’. Further quantitative research would be needed for that purpose. Our focus here is primarily on how the advocates of the movement succeeded in drawing attention to the concept. The study is based on a literature review and interviews.

The study suggests that the present position of green chemistry is in part due to an accidental combination of circumstances. Green chemistry was a child of the times and benefited from the fortuitous combination of an urgent social problem (the production of hazardous waste by the chemical industry) and a constructive solution (modifying chemical design so as to prevent the production and emission of hazardous waste). However, the fact that this concept, 25 years later, is viewed as a promising answer to these social issues is also due to strategic positioning, communication, and alliances by the advocates of the movement such as Paul Anastas of the EPA (Environmental Protection Agency) and the chemist John Warner. The following points illustrate how they reinforced the movement.

First of all, green chemistry combines a positive philosophy of chemistry with a practical approach. The concept expresses an optimistic and simple message: green chemistry ensures that no undesirable hazardous substances are released through the design of chemical products and processes. In other words, it offers the benefits provided by chemistry without the disadvantages. This message made it possible for a variety of interest groups to align themselves behind the goals of the movement. However, it was more than simply a matter of coming up with a feel-good philosophy: Anastas and Warner tied a concrete framework of action to the concept by formulating 12 design principles that provide practical tools for implementing green chemistry in practice. The message is: “green chemistry makes a better world possible – and this is how you do it!” (Again, this study was not intended to determine to what extent the movement actually contributed to making the world better but rather to explore how attention was focused on the overall message.)

Secondly, the design principles were formulated in such a manner that most of the competing professional disciplines fall within the definition of green chemistry. However, chemists have

criticised the 12 principles for giving a definition that was too broad. How many principles does a chemical process or product have to comply with in order to qualify as green chemistry? If only one of the 12 principles (such as the use of renewable raw materials) is applied in the design of a process or product, would it then count as green chemistry? And if not, what constitutes the dividing line? However, from the perspective of communication, this is actually a strong point. Thanks to the broad definition, any and all good examples from related professional disciplines can be gathered under the banner of green chemistry. As a result, green chemistry is able to position itself as the *precondition* for realising the guiding policy concepts of today, such as sustainability and circular economy.

A third point that is evident from the perspective of communication is that the added value of green chemistry is clearly defined for all target groups in their 'currency'. For the government green chemistry addresses the need to prevent the social costs of pollution, and it contributes to the legitimacy of the chemical sector. For researchers the concept offers new opportunities for research and innovation and at the same time allows chemists to demonstrate social responsibility. It offers the business sector a better image as well as significant cost savings. And finally, green chemistry offers citizens and environmental groups a tool for arguing that research and development should be based more on environmental considerations, so that they can also line up to support the goals of the movement. Clearly explaining the importance of the concept for various target groups, made it possible to gain the institutional support of a variety of interest groups. This was manifested by the launch of the Presidential Green Chemistry Challenge, and the support of stakeholder organisations such as the American Chemical Society (ACS) and the Green Chemistry and Commerce Council (GC3).

Expressing the added value of green chemistry in the target group's own currency leads to a virtuous cycle: the positioning of the concept as a policy goal (including financial support) captures the interest of researchers; the creation of a full-fledged research field gives the movement credibility and captures the interest of industry; concrete examples within the industry itself give the movement more visibility; positive messaging raises the level of trust in green chemistry; and this trust in turn enables more government support.

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Soft factors such as strategic positioning, communication, and the formation of alliances therefore appear to have had an influence on the rise of green chemistry as a movement within the field of chemistry. To what extent could the elements in the above analysis help in strengthening Safe-by-Design as a policy movement? The findings from the study lead to the following suggestions:

Figure 1: The 12 principles of green chemistry (source: www.epa.gov).

1. Create institutional support.

From the start, Anastas and Warner sought institutional support for green chemistry from a variety of interest groups. This institutional support gave the movement status and credibility. To further strengthen the support for Safe-by-Design, it could also make sense to explore whether comparable institutional support is possible in this case: are there important advocates for the movement from the research sector, the business community, or national or European policymakers who could provide high-level support?

2. Combine the positive association of Safe-by-Design with a practical approach.

As was the case for green chemistry in the 1990s, Safe-by-Design also seems to be a child of the times: the vision that products should be inherently safe can count on broad support from the government, the business community, civil society, and citizens. However – as was true of green chemistry in the 1990s – the concept is still in flux: it is not immediately clear to everyone what is meant by it or how you deal with it. The combination of a positive definition together with 12 concrete design principles facilitated the acceptance of green chemistry: it generated enthusiasm among potentially interested parties to participate in the movement and at the same time also made it clear what they had to do. Is it also possible to link the positive association of Safe-by-Design with a concrete action-based framework? Transparent communication can clarify to researchers and producers what Safe-by-Design actually means in terms of practical innovation.

3. Define the added value of Safe-by-Design for all target groups.

Green chemistry created a virtuous cycle by providing a clear definition of its message to all target groups in terms of each target group's own 'currency'. Is the added value of Safe-by-Design also clearly defined for all target groups? Is it, for example, clear how Safe-by-Design could lead to cost savings or new opportunities for innovation for the industry? Are there incentives for researchers to look at their research from a different perspective (such as subsidies, publication possibilities, or new opportunities for collaboration)?

4. Position Safe-by-Design vis-à-vis related movements.

The broad and inclusive definition of green chemistry ensured that the concept is seen as the *precondition* for realising the guiding policy concepts of today, such as sustainability and circular economy. Unambiguous positioning can clarify the specific significance and scope of a policy movement. What is the relationship between Safe-by-Design and related movements such as the Safe Innovation Approach, Regulatory Preparedness, and the Safe Chemicals Innovation Agenda? Should Safe-by-Design position itself as an independent movement or perhaps as an addition to existing concepts such as circular economy, green chemistry or sustainable chemistry? Various options are conceivable, but the historical origin of green chemistry suggests that a certain degree of continuity is needed to strengthen a policy movement over a longer period of time: besides its substantive meaning, the recognisability and visibility of the term are important.

Introduction

This report presents the results of a brief study into the rise and influence of green chemistry as a movement within the field of chemistry, and makes suggestions for strengthening the role of Safe-by-Design as an emerging policy approach. The concept has its origins in a growing environmental awareness within the chemical sector since the 1980s and 1990s. Its premise is to limit the negative effects of chemical products and processes on people and the environment as much as possible by already taking the harmful effects of chemical substances into account in the design phase. 25 years later, this approach is broadly supported, especially in the United States: green chemistry is solidly anchored as a policy guideline of the United States Environmental Protection Agency (EPA), as a research area within the field of chemistry, and as a design guideline for chemical innovation in the business sector.

The central question posed in this study was: what can we learn from the rise of green chemistry that would help us strengthen the role of Safe-by-Design as a design principle? The study approached green chemistry as a *movement*: it studied not only the substantive meaning of the term (e.g. the definition of the concept, the nature of the principles, and the various applications and savings realised) but in particular also the history of its origin, in other words: how did the concept originate? Who were the champions of the movement? How did they try to generate attention for the concept? After all, green chemistry is not the only policy movement that strives to formulate a greener vision of chemistry. It operates within a force field of competing movements such as clean chemistry, benign chemistry and sustainable chemistry. In this force field, broad-based policy movements such as bio-based economy, corporate social responsibility, responsible research and innovation and Safe-by-Design also play a role. These concepts all have their own substantive meaning, but they also serve as banners for various advocates to influence chemical policy, research, and innovation.

Figure 2: green chemistry overlaps competing movements in chemistry and policy.

This study is based on a review of the literature (a combination of literature from the socio-sciences and chemistry, grey literature, and online information) and interviews with researchers and policymakers.¹ The study was started in December 2017 and completed in April 2018.

This report presents the main findings of the study. After a brief description of the historical origins of the concept, an overview is given of how the advocates of green chemistry positioned and communicated the movement. The report then explores to what extent the elements of the analysis could help in strengthening Safe-by-Design as an emerging policy movement.

A brief history of green chemistry

The term ‘green chemistry’ has its origins in an increasing discontent with regard to the production and emission of hazardous waste by the chemical industry and associated environmental scandals. Examples include the Love Canal incident in Niagara Falls in 1978, where an entire residential neighbourhood had to be evacuated following the discovery of large quantities of heavily polluted chemical waste buried there, the disaster in Bhopal in 1984, where thousands of local residents died as a result of a gas leak in a factory of Union Carbide, and the discovery of dioxin pollution in Times Beach, Missouri, as a result of which the entire town had to be evacuated in 1983 (Sanderson, 2011).

In 1990, in response to such environmental issues, the Pollution Prevention Act was enacted, which represents a significant policy shift from ‘end-of-pipeline control’ to pollution prevention at the source (Linthorst, 2010). The societal costs of pollution were an important factor in this regard. The United States Congress viewed the prevention of the societal costs of environmental pollution as a shared interest of the government and the chemical industry. In the early 1990s, in response to the Pollution Prevention Act and a growing environmental awareness in chemistry, various environmental pressure groups emerged that focused on preventing the production and emission of hazardous substances. As chemistry lecturer Arjan Linthorst made clear in his historic study of green chemistry, the term has gained increasing popularity since the mid-1990s. The adjacent graph shows the number of scientific publications that refer to the various terms and makes clear that starting in 1997, the use of the term *green chemistry* rose sharply.

The graph prepared by Linthorst dates from 2010, and changes may have occurred in more recent years. Particularly in Europe, the term sustainable chemistry is becoming very popular, as witnessed by policy initiatives such

Figure 3: The use of ‘environmentally aware’ terms in scientific publications from 1988 to 2008. Source: Linthorst (2010).

¹ Thanks are due to: John Warner (Warner Babcock Institute for Green Chemistry), Frank Hollmann (Department of Biotechnology, TU Delft), Claire Skentelbery (Nanotechnology Industries Association), Peter van der Ham (Green Chemistry Campus), Adrienne Sips (RIVM) and Bart Walhout (RIVM) for their contributions to this study.

as the European Technology Platform for Sustainable Chemistry,² the German International Sustainable Chemistry Collaborative Centre,³ and the Sustainable Chemistry programme of TNO.⁴ The OECD (Organisation for Economic Cooperation and Development) also appears to prefer the term sustainable chemistry.⁵

Opinions differ regarding the degree of overlap between green chemistry and sustainable chemistry. Some view these terms as being synonymous. For example, on its website, the EPA writes: “Green chemistry is also known as sustainable chemistry.”⁶ Others make a clear distinction. For example, Petro Tundo writes as follows in his preface to a special issue of *Pure and applied chemistry*:

*“Recently, in fact, the difference between sustainable chemistry and green chemistry is becoming more evident. Sustainable chemistry envisions industrial processes that create better products, result in fewer pollutants, and are profitable. Green chemistry, in contrast, is more innovative. It deals with the fundamental aspects of chemistry without regard for industrial processes or profitability.”*⁷

The International Persistent Organic Pollutants Elimination Network (IPEN) supports the goals of green chemistry but not those of sustainable chemistry, because sustainable chemistry, according to IPEN, is much less concrete and therefore more susceptible to window dressing (see also p19 regarding “added value for citizens and civil society”).⁸ In contrast, a European Joint Working Group, established by CEN (European Committee for Standardisation) and the European Commission, recently proposed using the 12 design principles of green chemistry as a guideline to develop standards for ‘sustainable chemicals’.⁹

In any case, it is clear that green chemistry still has a solid basis today as a professional discipline within chemistry. Various scientific journals cover the topic, such as *Green Chemistry*¹⁰ and *Green Chemistry Letters and Reviews*.¹¹ Handbooks and edited volumes appear on a regular basis: recently the third edition of ‘*Green Chemistry: An Introductory Text*’ by Mike Lancaster appeared.¹² A great many congresses devoted to the topic take place each year, and institutes for green chemistry exist across the globe, including of course the green chemistry department of the EPA¹³ and the Green Chemistry Institute of the American Chemical Society,¹⁴ as well as GreenCentre Canada¹⁵ and the Centre for Green Chemistry at Monash University in Australia.¹⁶ The Safer Nanomaterials and Nanomanufacturing Initiative (SNNI) at the University of Oregon in the US aims to apply the principles of green chemistry to the development of safer

² <http://www.suschem.org/>

³ <https://www.isc3.org/en/home.html>

⁴ <https://www.tno.nl/en/focus-areas/industry/roadmaps/sustainable-chemical-industry/>

⁵ <http://www.oecd.org/chemicalsafety/risk-management/sustainablechemistry.htm>

⁶ <https://www.epa.gov/greenchemistry/basics-green-chemistry>

⁷ *Pure and applied chemistry*, Special issue, 79(11): 1831/2100.

https://www.iupac.org/publications/ci/2008/3002/bw1_bull.html

⁸ <http://ipen.org/sites/default/files/documents/IPEN%20Comments%20UNEA%20Green%20Chem%20Sustainable%20Chem%2030%20June%202017.pdf>

⁹ <http://nenmagazine.nen.nl/nenmagazine-2-2017#!/sustainable-chemicals>

¹⁰ <http://www.rsc.org/journals-books-databases/about-journals/green-chemistry/>

¹¹ <https://www.tandfonline.com/toc/tgcl/current>

¹² <http://pubs.rsc.org/en/content/ebook/978-1-78262-294-9>

¹³ <https://www.epa.gov/greenchemistry>

¹⁴ <https://www.acs.org/content/acs/en/greenchemistry.html>

¹⁵ <https://www.greencentrecanada.com/>

¹⁶ <http://www.monash.edu.au/strip/tenants/university/centre-greem-chemistry.html>

nanomaterials.¹⁷ There is also a Green Chemistry Campus in the Netherlands,¹⁸ although it should be noted that this innovation campus in Bergen op Zoom focuses primarily on the transition to renewable raw materials in the chemical sector (also referred to in the Netherlands as 'green' chemistry), and less on green chemistry as a design principle.

Figure 4: a sampling from the present range of activities on offer involving green chemistry: scientific journals, congresses, research institutes, and interest groups.

Findings

In this study, we looked for an answer to the question why green chemistry in particular is the term that is used most often – especially in the United States – instead of other competing movements in chemistry. Please note that the study at hand focused primarily on how the advocates of the movement succeeded in drawing green chemistry into the spotlight. The extent to which green chemistry actually contributes to making chemistry 'greener' is addressed here. Further research of a quantitative nature would be needed for that purpose.¹⁹

It should be noted that the rise of green chemistry was in part due to an accidental combination of circumstances. Green Chemistry was a child of the times (it was, as John Warner described it, a 'perfect storm'): in the first place, the pollution problems in the US demanded urgent solutions. In 1991, according to the EPA, an estimated 278 million tons of hazardous chemical waste was produced at 24,000 locations in the US, primarily by businesses (Sanderson, 2011). In addition, the Pollution Prevention Act of 1990 shifted the focus from end-of-pipe control to the prevention of pollution. There was therefore a clear need for solutions that could implement the policy goal of pollution prevention. Finally, there was significant funding available from the EPA for developing new solutions: over the years 1991, 1992, and 1993, the Pollution Prevention Act

¹⁷ <https://greennano.org/>

¹⁸ <https://www.greenchemistrycampus.com>

¹⁹ Critical voices can also be heard in this respect. Burnett (1998), for example, states that the value of the pollution prevention policy of the EPA is mostly symbolic.

made approximately 16 million dollars per year available for new solutions.²⁰ In other words, the world was ready for it. But in part the advocates of green chemistry, including Paul Anastas (employed as a policy officer at the EPA in the early 1990s) and John Warner (a research scientist for Polaroid at the time), reinforced the movement via strategic positioning and smart communication and by forming alliances. Some examples of how they managed to do so are presented below.

Definition: positive message and a practical approach

First of all, green chemistry combines a positive message with a practical approach. The definition embodies a very positive and deceptively simple message (Arjan Linthorst (2010) speaks of a clear ‘chemical philosophy’): green chemistry prevents the production and emission of hazardous substances via the intelligent design of chemical products and processes. In other words, it offers the benefits provided by chemistry without the disadvantages.

However, it is more than just a feel-good philosophy. In *Green Chemistry: Theory and Practice*,²¹ the highly cited work by Anastas and Warner from 1998, the positive definition is linked to a concrete framework of action via 12 design principles. This concrete framework of action differentiates green chemistry from movements such as Responsible Research and Innovation, which embody a comparable positive philosophy but do not immediately offer a concrete operational perspective. The message is: “a better world is possible – and this is how you do it!”²² (Please note that we are not dealing here with the question of whether the application of the design principles has also actually contributed to making the world better.) On its website, the American Chemical Society writes:

“The concept of greening chemistry is a relatively new idea which developed in the business and regulatory communities as a natural evolution of pollution prevention initiatives. In our efforts to improve crop protection, commercial products, and medicines, we also caused unintended harm to our planet and humans. By the mid-20th century, some of the long-term negative effects of these advancements could not be ignored. Pollution choked many of the world’s waterways and acid rain deteriorated forest health. There were measurable holes in the earth’s ozone. Some chemicals in common use were suspected of causing or directly linked to human cancer and other adverse human and environmental health outcomes. Many governments began to regulate the generation and disposal of industrial wastes and emissions. The United States formed the Environmental Protection Agency (EPA) in 1970, which was charged with protecting human and environmental health through setting and enforcing environmental regulations. Green chemistry takes the EPA’s mandate a step further and creates a new reality for chemistry and engineering by asking chemists and engineers to design chemicals, chemical processes and commercial products in a way that, at the very least, avoids the creation of toxics and waste. Green Chemistry is not politics. Green Chemistry is not a public relations ploy. Green chemistry is not a pipe dream. We are able to develop

²⁰ Pollution Prevention Act, § 13109. Authorization of appropriations: “There is authorized to be appropriated to the Administrator \$8,000,000 for each of the fiscal years 1991, 1992, and 1993 for functions carried out under this chapter (other than State Grants), (FOOTNOTE 1) and \$8,000,000 for each of the fiscal years 1991, 1992, and 1993, for grant programs to States issued pursuant to section 13104 of this title.” <https://www.epa.gov/p2/pollution-prevention-act-1990>

²¹ <https://global.oup.com/academic/product/green-chemistry-theory-and-practice-9780198506980?cc=nl&lang=en&>

²² See also Rusyn & Greene (2018), page 215: “As long as pollution prevention remains nothing more than a conceptual goal, it meets little resistance from affected parties; after all, it is hard to argue with the goal of reducing pollution for the betterment of all”.

chemical processes and earth-friendly products that will prevent pollution in the first place. Through the practice of green chemistry, we can create alternatives to hazardous substances we use as our source materials. We can design chemical processes that reduce waste and reduce demand on diminishing resources. We can employ processes that use smaller amounts of energy. We can do all of this and still maintain economic growth and opportunities while providing affordable products and services to a growing world population. This is a field open for innovation, new ideas, and revolutionary progress. This is the future of chemistry. This is green chemistry.”²³

Positioning: green chemistry as a precondition for sustainability policy goals

Secondly, the 12 design principles are themselves also an example of smart positioning: they are formulated in such a manner as to include most of the competing disciplines within the definition of green chemistry. However, chemists have criticised the 12 principles for giving a definition that was too broad. How many principles does a chemical process have to comply with in order to qualify as green chemistry? If only one of the 12 principles (such as the use of renewable raw materials) is applied in the design of a process or product, would it then count as green chemistry? And if not, what constitutes the dividing line? There are no clear indicators of the extent to which the 12 design principles have been applied to products or processes, as opposed to Cradle to Cradle, another design philosophy based on sustainability which actually works with five different levels of product certification.²⁴ However, from the perspective of communication, this is actually a strong point. Thanks to the broad definition, any and all good examples can be gathered under the banner of green chemistry (see Figure 5 and the discussion of the 12 principles in appendix 1). Strikingly, the lack of a clear answer to the question of when exactly a product or process complies with the guidelines of green chemistry has not had a negative impact on the concept. The opposite would seem to be true: the inclusiveness of the concept creates enough flexibility for related positive developments to become associated with green chemistry. For example, the article ‘The Greening of Chemistry’ in the journal *Distillations* of the Science History Institute mentions the cleaner production of ibuprofen as one of the success stories of green chemistry,²⁵ whereas in fact the example given predates the time that the term became accepted usage. The message is: atom economy, e-factors, bio catalysis, substitution, Cradle to Cradle - it’s all part of green chemistry! The movement positions itself as a necessary *precondition* for realising guiding policy concepts of our time, such as sustainability and circular economy. Interestingly, green chemistry is presented as an entirely new professional discipline and not as a collage of existing practices.

Figure 5: The 12 design principles of green chemistry are ‘inclusive’.

²³ <https://www.acs.org/content/acs/en/greenchemistry/what-is-green-chemistry.html>

²⁴ <https://www.c2ccertified.org/>

²⁵ <https://www.sciencehistory.org/distillations/magazine/the-greening-of-chemistry>

Few references are made to the legacy of environmental chemistry and philosophy from the 1980s. “Green” pioneers in chemistry prior to the rise of green chemistry such as Kenneth Hancock (former director of the Chemistry Department of the National Science Foundation in the US), Barry Trost (the chemist who introduced the atom economy concept)²⁶ or Roger Sheldon (originator of the E-factor)²⁷ are mentioned but primarily within the context of their contribution to green chemistry.

Note that safety plays a role in various principles of green chemistry (also see appendix 1), such as:

- Principle 4: *Design Benign Chemicals: Design chemical products that are fully effective yet have little or no toxicity.* This principle introduces safety as a design issue. As such, it therefore connects with Safe-by-Design. On the ACS website, Nicholas D. Anastas, a co-worker of the EPA, writes: ‘hazard is a design flaw and must be addressed at the genesis of molecular design.’²⁸ Safety is therefore a question of smart design and requires a different mindset from chemists
- Principle 11: ***Real-time Analysis for Pollution Prevention: Include in-process, real-time monitoring and control during syntheses to minimize or eliminate the formation of byproducts.*** This principle focuses on the development of measuring and analysis methods for monitoring and controlling the formation of hazardous substances during the chemical design process. It therefore contains elements of analytical chemistry and process technology. It also intersects with the manner in which Safe-by-Design is presently being implemented in European initiatives such as NanoReg2: make effective use of the instruments available for monitoring the potential risks during the various stages of technological development. (Although it should be noted that principle 11 focuses primarily on the management of the production process, whereas NanoReg2 deals primarily with the various phases of research and innovation. However, the idea behind both is similar: aim to learn as much as possible about the properties of your reaction and possible unintended effects or by-products make sure during the production and/or innovation process.)
- Principle 12: ***Inherently Benign Chemistry for Accident Prevention: Design chemicals and their physical forms (solid, liquid, or gas) to minimize the potential for chemical accidents including explosions, fires, and releases to the environment.*** This principle is known as the ‘safety principle’: it aims to build safety into the choice and design of chemical substances, but also includes the broader Occupational Health and Safety regulations. As remarked by Shelly Bradley, David Finster and Tom Goodwin on the ACS (American Chemical Society) website, this principle is generally overlooked. Wrongly so, according to the authors, as the essence of green chemistry is to reduce or prevent the production of hazardous substances, which means that it is intrinsically linked to safety in the laboratory and on the shop floor. In their words: “*The Hierarchy of Safety Controls as highlighted in the Occupational Safety and Health Administration (OSHA)’s new Transitioning to Safer Chemicals Toolkit illustrates the difference between focusing on the control or hazard part of the safety definition. Traditional*

²⁶ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Barry_Trost

²⁷ <http://www.sheldon.nl/roger/index.html>

²⁸ <https://www.acs.org/content/acs/en/greenchemistry/what-is-green-chemistry/principles/gc-principle-of-the-month-4.html>

chemical safety models focus primarily on the control component of that definition. The graphic (adapted from OSHA) shows that the most effective means of increasing safety is eliminating the hazard component. Since the elimination of hazards is the basic tenet of Green Chemistry, this marriage of the ideas of Green Chemistry from both OSHA and EPA should have a synergistic impact on hazard reduction. Combining the forces of these two agencies toward a common goal may lead to conversations and changes that result in safer conditions for workers, a safer environment for the general public, and a safer planet for us all."

Figure 6: The hierarchy of safety measures according to the American Occupational Safety and Health Administration (OSHA). Source: www.acs.org.

Safety is also included in other principles, such as principle 3: ‘Design less hazardous chemical syntheses’, and principle 5: ‘Use safer solvents and reaction conditions’. Safety is therefore – at least in theory - an essential element of the philosophy of green chemistry. Nevertheless, it appears that in practice green chemistry is based more on *sustainability* aspects than on safety considerations. In an interview, John Warner did explain that safety for the industry is potentially an important driver, in particular if you can provide a mechanism with which the industry can determine at an early stage whether a substance or product is safe.

Communication: added value is clear to all target groups.

A third point that becomes evident if we look at the positioning of green chemistry is that the added value of the term is clearly defined for all target groups in terms of the target group’s own ‘currency’ . Here again, this is due in part to the spirit of the times but in part also to strategic positioning.

Added value for the government

For the government green chemistry is a way to prevent the societal costs of pollution. It also contributes to the legitimacy of the chemical sector. Building further on the Pollution Prevention

Act, Anastas *cum suis* took advantage of this policy space to look for high-level support from the beginning. This led, among other things, to the launch of the Presidential Green Chemistry Award under the presidency of Clinton in 1995,²⁹ a competition for the best projects in the area of green chemistry. This award provided name recognition and at the same time generated a continuous stream of pilot projects, all of which were grouped under the banner of green chemistry.

Added value for researchers

For researchers, green chemistry embodies the social responsibility of chemists, while at the same time providing new opportunities for research and innovation. According to Sanderson (2011), the success of green chemistry is due to the positioning of the term as a field of research, thereby differentiating it from political or social movements. Linthorst (2010) also argues that its development as a research field was an important success factor. For example, in the early period (1993-94), the EPA organised international symposia to help flesh out the content and direction of the concept.³⁰ In addition, green chemistry was also incorporated as a core policy of the American Chemical Society. It should be noted that the English Royal Society of Chemistry also played an important role in the establishment of green chemistry as a legitimate area of scientific research by launching the scientific journal *Green Chemistry*.

Through the organisation of scientific symposia, research subsidies, and new publication opportunities (the researchers' own 'currency'), green chemistry gained a solid base as a field of research within chemistry.

Nevertheless, some chemists remain sceptical with regard to green chemistry: they see it as a form of political correctness or as a new hype intended to attract research funding, although the attitude seems to change as more examples of practical applications take root. As green chemistry is so dependent on the mindset of chemists, its advocates spend a great deal of energy on training within green chemistry. Traditionally, chemists are not trained to think in terms of product or process design or life-cycle concepts. And even if they do follow safety courses, then it's about working safely in the laboratory. The organisation *Beyond benign*,³¹ another brainchild of John Warner, is completely focused on giving the new generation of chemists a broader perspective in which toxicology, environmental chemistry, and design are an integral part of education in chemistry. As is made clear by the discussion of the principles of green chemistry in appendix 1, several of the principles (such as Principles 4, 7, 9 and 10) try to broaden the mindset of chemists: by integrating environmental chemistry, catalysis and bio-

Figure 7: The EPA helps to establish a permanent base for green chemistry by making research subsidies available.

²⁹ <https://www.epa.gov/greenchemistry/information-about-presidential-green-chemistry-challenge>

³⁰ One such symposium was held in 1993, 'Benign by Design: Alternative Synthetic Design for Pollution Prevention', in Chicago.

³¹ <http://www.beyondbenign.org/about-green-chemistry/>

based economy as central design principles in chemistry, these fields of research are incorporated as an essential part of chemistry.

Added value for the business sector

For the business sector, green chemistry offers a better image and, perhaps more importantly, significant cost savings. Modern-day applications of green chemistry can be found in particular in the replacement of conventional more polluting methods by less toxic alternatives, for example the use of supercritical CO₂: at high temperatures and pressures, CO₂ behaves as a gas as well as a liquid. This makes it an effective solvent for a broad range of organic as well as an inorganic reactions. Ionic liquids are another example of more environmentally friendly alternatives for solvents. Gujral et al (2012) also refer to the use of hydrogen peroxide solutions as an oxidiser and the use of hydrogen in asymmetric synthesis.³²

Over the years, the Green Chemistry Challenge has generated a variety of results. The American pharmaceutical company Pfizer has realised major cost savings thanks to modifications in the production of medicines. The environmental factor or E-factor, i.e. the number of kilograms of waste produced for manufacturing a kilogram of product can vary between 25 and 100 for the

Figure 8: Pfizer became a strong advocate of green chemistry.

production of medicines. So there are clearly significant opportunities for costs reductions here. When first synthesised by Pfizer, Viagra had an E-factor of 105. By replacing harmful solvents and recovering and reusing various substances, the E-factor for Viagra was reduced to 8. In 2001, this success led to Pfizer implementing a more systematic green chemistry drive. The E-factor for Lyrica, a medicine that is used to treat nerve pain and epilepsy, was reduced from 86 to 9. Comparable reductions were realised for the antidepressant sertraline and the anti-inflammatory celecoxib. According to Peter Dunn, research manager for green chemistry at Pfizer, Pfizer produces half a million tons less of chemical waste thanks to the improvements for

these three products alone.³³ This was the starting sign for Pfizer's Green Journey, in the course of which significant cost savings have been realised for various products.

At the giant German chemical company BASF, green chemistry also plays an important role. In 2002, BASF introduced a process that uses ionic liquids at ambient temperature to remove acidic byproducts from reaction mixtures. According to researcher Pete Licence of the University of Nottingham, BASF takes a systematic approach in dealing with the interrelationships between the various processes in a chemical plant. In an integrated reaction system, the products and byproducts of reactions can be recycled in adjoining facilities, and residual energy from one process can be used to heat the next reaction.

³² Gujral, S.A., M.A. Sheela, Smriti Khatri, Rajeev K Singla (2012) A Focus & Review on the Advancement of Green Chemistry. Indo Global Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences, 2(4): 397-408.

³³ Dunn, P. (2012) The importance of Green Chemistry in Process Research and Development. Chem. Soc. Rev., 2012,41, 1452-1461.

Note in this regard that making processes “greener” is always a compromise between benefits, feasibility, and costs. The need for the large-scale restructuring of chemical processes explains why the transition to green chemistry is not always a simple matter. For the production of bulk chemicals, such a transition involves huge volumes, largely optimised processes (with E-factors between 1 and 5), and huge investments. Although it is generally possible to introduce further optimisation (up to an E-factor of 0.1), doing so is often not profitable in view of the long-term investments already made. Production facilities are often built to operate for 30 or 40 years. Investments are also not without risk, as promising innovations may turn out not to be cost-effective in practice, leading to a loss of the investment. Technical barriers also exist, as environmentally friendly alternatives for toxic solvents are not always available.

The application of green chemistry by the industry has until now been primarily a question of incremental changes to existing processes. The real green revolution, in which chemical processes are completely redesigned and production facilities are built from scratch, is yet to be realised.

Added value for citizens and civil society

Finally, the message for citizens and environmental organisations is that green chemistry allows for environmental considerations to play an important role in research and development. This

Figure 9: Environmental organisations such as the International Persistent Organic Pollutants Elimination Network (IPEN) also support green chemistry. Like Pfizer, it became a strong advocate of green chemistry.

approach to chemistry is also in line with the interests of civil society. Environmental organisations such as the International Persistent Organic Pollutants Elimination Network (IPEN) have mobilised themselves behind the goals of green chemistry.

Interestingly, the IPEN supports green chemistry but at the same time criticises sustainable chemistry because sustainable chemistry is much less concrete and, according to the IPEN,

therefore more susceptible to window dressing. For example, in a commentary on green chemistry for the United Nations, the IPEN writes:

“Sustainable chemistry has only been vaguely defined, leaving the term open to any number of interpretations, including chemistries that do nothing to reduce harm. [...] This] invites labeling all kinds of current chemistries as sustainable chemistry, watering down the term to render it nearly useless and leaving opportunities to “greenwash” chemistries with a term that suggests social or environmental benefits that do not exist.”³⁴

This quote emphasises the importance of the link between a feel-good philosophy and concrete results.

³⁴ <http://ipen.org/sites/default/files/documents/IPEN%20Comments%20UNEA%20Green%20Chem%20Sustainable%20Chem%2030%20June%202017.pdf>

A virtuous cycle

As the added value of green chemistry can be expressed in the target groups' own currency, we end up with a virtuous cycle. The positioning of green chemistry as a policy goal attracts the interest of the research sector. The development of a full-fledged research field provides the movement with credibility and attracts the interest of industry. Concrete examples of projects within the industry raise the profile of the movement (see for example the comments from the World Economic Forum on "4 ways green chemistry is helping make the world a better place").³⁵ Positive messaging in the media increases public trust in green chemistry, and that trust in turn makes further government support possible, and so forth.

Figure 10: A virtuous cycle occurs if the added value can be expressed in the target groups' own currency.

Conclusion

This brief review suggests that the broad support for green chemistry by the government, the research sector, the business sector and civil society, particularly in the United States, is in part due to an accidental combination of circumstances. Green chemistry was a child of the times and benefited from the fortuitous combination of an urgent social problem (the production and emission of hazardous waste by the chemical industry) and a constructive solution (modifying chemical design so as to prevent the production and emission of hazardous waste). But the fact that green chemistry in particular is seen as the precondition for the realisation of guiding policy concepts such as sustainability and circular economy, is also due in part to strategic positioning, effective alliance formation, and smart communication on the part of the advocates of the movement. The timeline below presents a number of significant milestones in the development of green chemistry. The timeline shows how the concept developed over time from *one* possible answer to the Pollution Prevention Act in the early 1990s to *the definite* answer to the Pollution

³⁵ <https://www.weforum.org/agenda/2016/10/4-ways-green-chemistry-is-helping-make-the-world-a-better-place/>

Prevention Act, as it is now generally presented by its advocates. It should be noted that green chemistry became the obvious answer several years after the enactment of the Pollution Prevention Act. During the intervening period, the term was not so self-evident. The EPA research programme in 1993-1994, for example, dealt with 'benign chemistry'. It is also an open question to what extent its principles relate to the original text of the Pollution Prevention Act, which primarily expressed a general ambition to prevent pollution. In any case, thanks to the advocates of the movement, green chemistry (at least in the US) is seen as the obvious answer to these challenges .

Figure 11: Timeline of green chemistry.

The combination of a feel-good philosophy with a practical approach encouraged researchers and developers to apply the design principles of green chemistry in the practice of innovation. The fact that the added value could be expressed in the target group's own currency helped in convincing the representatives of the various stakeholders concerned to align themselves behind the movement. Institutional support by the EPA, the American Chemical Society (ACS), and the Green Chemistry and Commerce Council (GC3) gave the movement status and credibility. The Presidential Green Chemistry Challenge generated a continuous stream of examples of concrete applications. Finally, success stories from the business sector further raised the profile of green chemistry. Soft factors therefore appear to have had an influence on the rise of green chemistry as a movement within chemistry as a whole.

Learning from green chemistry for Safe-by-Design?

To what extent could the elements in the above analysis help in strengthening Safe-by-Design as a policy movement? It is not our intention here to suggest that green chemistry and Safe-by-Design are identical concepts. Although there are similarities, there are also differences. The historical origins of the two concepts differ, they are based on different considerations, and they play a role in different societal contexts. In addition, it is quite conceivable that green chemistry was able to blossom due to the specific political, legal, and commercial context in the United States. It may not be so simple to translate measures that worked effectively in the US to the

European playing field. Nevertheless, the findings from the study at hand could lead to some suggestions for Safe-by-Design as an emerging policy movement, which are summarised in the following four lessons.

1. Create institutional support.

Institutional support for green chemistry gave the movement status and credibility. To further strengthen the basis of support for Safe-by-Design, it could also make sense to explore whether comparable institutional support is conceivable:

- Are there national or European policymakers that could provide high-level support? Safe-by-Design plays a role in the Addressing Safety Consciously programme of the Ministry of Infrastructure and Water Management.³⁶ The NMBP programme of the European Commission has also funded various projects dealing with Safe-by-Design.³⁷
- Can important advocates for the movement be found in the field of research or the business sector? Potential candidates include the KNCV (Royal Netherlands Chemical Society), the VSNU (Association of Universities in the Netherlands), and the KNAW (Royal Netherlands Academy of Arts and Sciences) in the case of research, or organisations such as the VNCI (Royal Association of the Dutch Chemical Industry) or VNO-NCW (Confederation of Netherlands Industry and Employers) for the business sector, in which Safe-by-Design is already a topic of discussion to a greater or lesser degree.
- Is there supporting legislation? Could REACH³⁸ provide support for Safe-by-Design, in the way the Pollution Prevention Act provided policy and financial support for green chemistry?

2. Combine a positive definition with a practical approach.

As was the case for green chemistry in the 1990s, Safe-by-Design also seems to be a child of the times: the vision that products should be inherently safe can count on broad support from the government, the business community, civil society, and citizens. However – as was true of green chemistry in the 1990s – the concept is still in flux: it is not immediately clear to everyone what is meant by it or how you deal with it.

The combination of a positive definition together with 12 concrete design principles facilitated the acceptance of green chemistry: it generated enthusiasm among potentially interested parties to participate in the movement and at the same time also made it clear what they had to do. Is it also possible to link the positive association of Safe-by-Design with a concrete action-based framework? Is it clear what researchers and producers have to *do* if they wish to implement Safe-by-Design? Is there a general introduction available, for example in the form of a clearly laid out website, handbook, or training, that explains what the concept means and how researchers and developers can integrate the principle into their work activities? A quick Internet search suggests that although a great deal of material can be found on the subject, the material is primarily of an academic nature, for example in the form of research reports, reports of European projects such as NanoReg, and reviews in scientific journals. This material does not

³⁶ <https://www.rijksoverheid.nl/onderwerpen/gezonde-en-veilige-leefomgeving/documenten/rapporten/2017/08/23/programma-bewust-omgaan-met-veiligheid>

³⁷ NMBP stands for Nanotechnologies, Advanced Materials, Biotechnology and Advanced Manufacturing and Processing. An open call for Safe by Design can be found at: <http://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/portal/desktop/en/opportunities/h2020/topics/nmbp-15-2019.html>.

³⁸ REACH is a regulation of the European Union that aims to protect the health of humans and the environment from the potential risks of chemical substances. REACH stands for Registration, Evaluation, Authorisation and Restriction of Chemicals. See: <https://echa.europa.eu/nl/regulations/reach/understanding-reach>.

immediately make it clear to newcomers what the term really means and what its added value might be. Clear communication can explain to researchers and producers what Safe-by-Design actually means in terms of practical innovation.

3. Define the added value for all target groups.

Green chemistry created a virtuous cycle because the message was clearly defined for all target groups in terms of each group's own 'currency'. Is the added value of Safe-by-Design also clearly defined for all target groups? Is it, for example, clear how Safe-by-Design could lead to cost savings or new opportunities for innovation for the industry? Can concrete examples be named of cost savings realised? And how could researchers be motivated to integrate Safe-by-Design into their daily research practice? Are there incentives for researchers to look at their research from a different perspective (such as subsidies, publication possibilities, or new opportunities for collaboration)?

4. Determine the position with reference to related movements.

The broad and inclusive definition of green chemistry ensured that the concept is seen as the *precondition* subject to which the guiding policy concepts of today, such as sustainability and circular economy, can be realised. Unambiguous positioning can clarify the specific significance and scope of a policy movement. Should Safe-by-Design position itself as an independent movement or perhaps as an addition to existing concepts such as circular economy, green chemistry or sustainable chemistry? What is the relationship between Safe-by-Design and related movements such as the Safe Innovation Approach, Regulatory Preparedness, or the Safe Chemicals Innovation Agenda? In fact, various principles of green chemistry focus on safety: Safe-by-Design could, for example, be positioned as an essential link in this overall movement - as the practical implementation of these three principles. Various options are conceivable, but the historical origin of green chemistry shows that a certain degree of continuity is needed to strengthen a policy movement over a longer period of time: besides its substantive meaning, the recognisability and visibility of the term are important.

Figure 12: What is the relationship between Safe-by-Design and related policies?

Appendix 1: The 12 principles of green chemistry

The 12 principles of green chemistry that can be found on the website of the American Chemical Society are described below,³⁹ followed by a brief discussion of each principle.

1. Prevent waste: Design chemical syntheses to prevent waste. Leave no waste to treat or clean up.

This principle aims to design chemical processes in such a manner that the production and emission of chemical waste is reduced or even completely prevented. This principle has much in common with the cradle-to-cradle design principle of William McDonough and Michael Braungart,⁴⁰ and with the concept of a circular economy. According to Berkeley W. Cue Jr. of BWC Pharma Consulting, this is the most important principle. The other principles primarily explain *how* you can achieve this.⁴¹

2. Maximize atom economy: Design syntheses so that the final product contains the maximum proportion of the starting materials. Waste few or no atoms.

Principle 2 deals with the *reactants*. Chemists should focus not only on the yield of a reaction but also on the atom economy of the reaction, the degree to which the atoms in the reaction end up in the product. The atom economy concept was introduced in 1991 by Barry M. Trost.⁴² Another metric often used is the E-factor, defined by Roger Sheldon as the formula weight of the product divided by the formula weight of all reactants.⁴³

3. Design less hazardous chemical syntheses: Design syntheses to use and generate substances with little or no toxicity to either humans or the environment.

This principle focuses on the chemical *design process*. David Constable, Director of the ACS Green Chemistry Institute, writes: *"It's not that adhering to this principle is particularly difficult to do; it's more that chemists are disinterested in doing it. For the synthetic organic chemist, effecting a successful chemical transformation in a new way or with a new molecule or in a new order is what matters. [...] This principle is asking chemists to broaden their definition of what constitutes good science."*⁴⁴ This principle therefore introduces a different perspective on 'what matters' in chemistry. It makes it clear that making chemistry 'greener' depends in large part on a cultural shift in chemistry.

4. Design safer chemicals and products: Design chemical products that are fully effective yet have little or no toxicity.

³⁹ https://www.acs.org/content/acs/en/greenchemistry/what-is-green-chemistry/principles/12-principles-of-green-chemistry.html#articleContent_columnbootstrap_0

⁴⁰ <http://www.cradletocradle.com/>

⁴¹ <https://www.acs.org/content/acs/en/greenchemistry/what-is-green-chemistry/principles/gc-principle-of-the-month-1.html>

⁴² The Atom Economy - A Search for Synthetic Efficiency; Barry M. Trost; *Science* 1991, (254), pp 1471-1477.

⁴³ <http://www.sheldon.nl/roger/efactor.html>

⁴⁴ <https://www.acs.org/content/acs/en/greenchemistry/what-is-green-chemistry/principles/green-chemistry-principle-3.html>

This principle deals with the *products*. It introduces safety as a design principle and as a result interfaces with Safe-by-Design. Nicholas D. Anastas, co-worker at the EPA, writes as follows on the ACS website: *“Minimizing toxicity, while simultaneously maintaining function and efficacy, may be one of the most challenging aspects of designing safer products and processes. Achieving this goal requires an understanding of not only chemistry but also of the principles of toxicology and environmental science. [...] Mastering the art and science of toxicology requires innovative approaches to chemical characterization that state that **hazard is a design flaw and must be addressed at the genesis of molecular design**. The intrinsic hazard of elements and molecules is a fundamental chemical property that must be characterized, evaluated and managed as part of a systems-based strategy for chemical design.”*⁴⁵ Here again, the approach to design requires a different mindset from chemists.

5. Use safer solvents and reaction conditions: Avoid using solvents, separation agents, or other auxiliary chemicals. If you must use these chemicals, use safer ones.

This principle deals with the *reagents / solvents*. It contains elements of substitution-based thinking and chemical alternatives. Ms Concepción Jiménez-González, Director of Operational Sustainability at GlaxoSmithKline, writes: *“solvents account for about 75% of the cumulative life cycle environmental impacts of a standard batch chemical operation. [...] The object is to choose solvents that make sense chemically, reduce the energy requirements, have the least toxicity, have the fewest life cycle environmental impacts and don't have major safety impacts.”*⁴⁶ As the experiences of Peter Dunn at Pfizer suggests, it is this search for less harmful solvents in particular that has resulted in major cost savings for the industry.

6. Increase energy efficiency: Run chemical reactions at room temperature and pressure whenever possible.

According to David Constable, this is one of the forgotten principles of green chemistry: *“Energy—like thinking about how to arrange a synthesis to have the fewest number of steps, or use the lowest cost starting materials or any other aspect of interest to the synthetic or process chemist—is just another design parameter. Historically it has not been seen as that, but we can no longer afford to design new molecules in the absence of a detailed and extended consideration of how energy will be used.”*⁴⁷ The article by Sanderson (2011) briefly explains how the recycling of heat at BASF has led to cost savings.

7. Use renewable feedstocks: Use starting materials (also known as feedstocks) that are renewable rather than depletable. The source of renewable feedstocks is often agricultural products or the wastes of other processes; the source of depletable feedstocks is often fossil fuels (petroleum, natural gas, or coal) or mining operations.

⁴⁵ <https://www.acs.org/content/acs/en/greenchemistry/what-is-green-chemistry/principles/gc-principle-of-the-month-4.html>

⁴⁶ <https://www.acs.org/content/acs/en/greenchemistry/what-is-green-chemistry/principles/green-chemistry-principle-5.html>

⁴⁷ <https://www.acs.org/content/acs/en/greenchemistry/what-is-green-chemistry/principles/green-chemistry-principle-6.html>

This principle formulates in large part the goals of the bio-based economy, and is closely aligned with what is meant in the Netherlands by 'green' chemistry: the transition from fossil-based starting materials to renewable starting materials. This principle, like principle 1, clearly has much in common with concepts such as the circular economy, the cradle-to-cradle philosophy of William McDonough and Michael Braungart.

8. Avoid chemical derivatives: Avoid using blocking or protecting groups or any temporary modifications if possible. Derivatives use additional reagents and generate waste.

For Peter Dunn, leader of the Green Chemistry programme at Pfizer, this is one of the key principles of green chemistry. It has in any case led to major cost savings in the pharmaceutical industry. Dunn refers to the synthesis of semisynthetic antibiotics as an example: *"More than 10,000 metric tons of 6-APA is made every year and much of it by the greener enzymatic process so this is a fantastic example of Green Chemistry making a real difference"*.⁴⁸

9. Use catalysts, not stoichiometric reagents: Minimize waste by using catalytic reactions. Catalysts are effective in small amounts and can carry out a single reaction many times. They are preferable to stoichiometric reagents, which are used in excess and carry out a reaction only once.

This principle actually comprises the entire field of research involving catalysis. Roger Sheldon, Emeritus Professor of Bio-catalysis and Organic Chemistry at TU Delft, explains on the ACS website that this principle actually represents a paradigm shift with regard to the concept of efficiency in organic synthesis: from a focus on chemical yield to a focus on minimising waste. Sheldon expects catalysts, and in particular enzymes, to play an important role in the transition to the bio-based economy.

10. Design chemicals and products to degrade after use: Design chemical products to break down to innocuous substances after use so that they do not accumulate in the environment.

This principle aims to take into account the potential negative consequences of end-of-life degradation products early on in the design process. As a result, environmental chemistry and toxicology become an essential part of chemical design. Rich Williams, Director of Environmental Science & Green Chemistry Consulting, writes: *"Biodegradation, hydrolysis, and photolysis can be designed into chemical products. In the same way that mechanistic toxicology knowledge is essential to identify and design out molecular features that are the basis for hazards, an understanding of the mechanisms of degradation and persistence are required to design in chemical features that promote degradation and eliminate features that promote persistence. [...] Prediction methods that can guide the design of molecular architecture expected to degrade include rules of thumb linking structural features to degradability or persistence, databases of existing knowledge, models that evaluate*

⁴⁸ https://www.acs.org/content/acs/en/greenchemistry/what-is-green-chemistry/principles/green-chemistry-principle--8.html#articleContent_headingtext

biodegradability or PBT attributes, and experimental testing. All of these tools can be adapted to individual chemical sectors and specific objectives.”

11. Analyse in real time to prevent pollution: Include in-process, real-time monitoring and control during syntheses to minimize or eliminate the formation of byproducts.

This principle focuses on the development of *measuring and analysis methods* for monitoring and controlling the formation of hazardous substances during the chemical design process. Douglas Raynie, Department Head of Chemistry and Biochemistry at South Dakota State University, writes as follows on the ACS website: *“Just as we need real-time feedback for driving safety, real-time feedback is essential in proper functioning chemical processes. Most chemists are familiar with laboratory analysis from their undergraduate training. But analysis can also be performed in-line, on-line, or at-line in a chemical plant, a subdiscipline known as process analytical chemistry. Such analysis can detect changes in process temperature or pH prior to a reaction going out of control, poisoning of catalysts can be determined, and other deleterious events can be detected before a major incident occurs.”* This principle therefore contains elements of analytical chemistry and process technology. It tries to make effective use of the available instruments to monitor the potential risks during the various stages of technological development: aim to learn as much as possible about the properties of your reaction and possible unintended effects or by-products during the production and/or innovation process.⁴⁹

12. Minimize the potential for accidents: Design chemicals and their physical forms (solid, liquid, or gas) to minimize the potential for chemical accidents including explosions, fires, and releases to the environment.

This principle is known as the ‘safety principle’: it aims to build safety into the choice and design of chemical substances, but also includes the broader Occupational Health and Safety regulations. As remarked by Shelly Bradley, David Finster and Tom Goodwin on the ACS website,⁵⁰ this principle is generally overlooked. Wrongly so, according to the authors, as the essence of green chemistry is to reduce or prevent the production of hazardous substances, which means that it is intrinsically linked to safety in the laboratory and on the shop floor. In their words: *“Traditional chemical safety models focus primarily on the control component of that definition. Since the elimination of hazards is the basic tenet of Green Chemistry, this marriage of the ideas of Green Chemistry from both OSHA and EPA should have a synergistic impact on hazard reduction. Combining the forces of these two agencies toward a common goal may lead to conversations and changes that result in safer conditions for workers, a safer environment for the general public, and a safer planet for us all.”*

⁴⁹ <http://www.nanoreg2.eu/>

⁵⁰ <https://www.acs.org/content/acs/en/greenchemistry/what-is-green-chemistry/principles/green-chemistry-principle--12.html>

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